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A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF COMMUNICATION IN ANY ORGANISATION IN THE PAST WITH THE PRESENT WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO ODISHA WATERSHED DEVELOPMENT MISSION'S PROJECT "WORLP"

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Abstract:

Initially Orissa Watershed Development Mission did not have proper working modalities and operational Guidelines on management of watershed projects. The staffs did not have adequate knowledge and expertise on management of different projects resulting in poor work quality and Planning. Poor organisational structure and lack of team work lead to poor progress. Communication was limited within few departmental staffs of the organisation. The organisation did not show any interest for building capacity of Managers, Assistant Managers, supervisors and the district level staffs. Less transparency and poor accountability were there. There was not adequate resource for printing and publication purpose.

The Objective of the Study is to compare the communication process adopted in OWDM in the past with the present. The focus will also be to know about various communication strategy adopted during the implementation of WORLP. Personal Discussions, interviews, small interactions with the employees of Odisha Watershed Development Mission and the project staffs. The research is more of qualitative in nature by going through the past history of the organisation with the present situation with some of its future implication.

Key words: WORLP, OWDM, watershed, ODISHA.

Introduction

Watershed is an area from where all rain water runoff flows into a single stream. Watershed Development activities involve management of natural resources like soil and water along with various agronomical interventions with a focus on livelihoods improvement where communities are involved in participatory planning and implementation of watershed programmes. Watershed development programmes funded through various sources were executed in Orissa through District Rural Development Agencies [DRDAs] and the Directorate of Soil Conservation. Though execution of watersheds was in adherence to the prescribed guidelines of Government of India, management related gaps persisted in the process of implementation. There was no 'single window' system to monitor all the watersheds implemented under different government and non-government schemes. Also, convergence in thematic areas i.e. both technical and non-technical was lacking. Keeping this in view, the **Orissa Watershed Development Mission** (OWDM) was constituted under the Department of Agriculture, Government of Orissa, for planning, implementing and monitoring all Watershed Development Programmes in the State. The OWDM was constituted by the Govt. of Orissa as a registered Society and came into existence on 30th June, 2000.

Recognizing the importance of Watershed Development as a platform for poverty alleviation, the Government of Orissa created the OWDM to give a "Strategic focus to the programme to be operated in Mission mode". The mission intends to provide the required focus, coordination and operational flexibilities in implementation of watershed concepts and approaches in the State. Western Orissa Rural Livelihood Project (WORLP), a Government of Orissa initiative is managed by Orissa Watershed Development Mission. It is a joint venture of Government of Orissa and the UK Department For International Development (DFID). Technical Assistance and consultancy support to the project is provided by NR International of UK. The project was inaugurated in August 2000 and full scale field implementation began in October 2001. It worked in four project districts; Bargarh, Bolangir, Kalahandi and Nuapara who are among the poorest in Orissa. Poor health indicators, erratic rain fall, lack of irrigation facility resulting in drought like situation, shortage of safe drinking facility, inequitable social structures, distorted land distribution, indebtedness, gender and other inequities contribute to the widespread poverty in Western Orissa and impede access by poor and marginalised people to resources.

Vision

To bring about social and economic transformation of the people in the State of Odisha by creating an enabling environment for development of sustainable natural resources, effective social mobilization and people centred institutions through Watershed based approaches.

Mission

To enhance the productivity of rain fed /degraded lands and livelihoods opportunities for the poor and marginalised through participatory watershed management.

To improve the quality and process of watershed development programmes in the state by providing required focus on watershed concepts and approaches, co-ordination and operational guidance in planning, implementation and monitoring.

Goal

The goal of Odisha Watershed Development Mission is to act as a facilitating organisation with the responsibility of creating knowledge and resources by collaborating with agencies having expertise in various aspects of watershed development, to function as an integral part of Government of Odisha with adequate operational autonomy regarding interpretation of guidelines and with the accountability of improving the quality and process of watershed development programmes in the state.

WESTERN ORISSA RURAL LIVELIHOODS PROJECT : OPERATIONAL DISTRICTS ORGANISATIONAL STRUCTURE OF ODISHA WATERSHED DEVELOPMENT MISSION
Structure of OWDM in the past

Structure during WORLP

Literature Survey:

http://stephenjgill.typepad.com/performance_improvement_b/2008/12-communication_problems_in_organisations.html#sthash.mNOVekrL.dpuf

The literature says about the different communication problem occur in organisations ,the challenges people face in organisation. An analysis of responses from 15 organisation leaders identified 9 categories like not all the employees are always informed, employees not receiving consistent and timely messages from management, right information not sent to right people, expectations are not clear, future plan is unknown, functional areas not collaborating, lack of openness, communication hamper due to distance factor.

Article on Research in Organisations: The article says about different types of communication an organisation like upward, downward and horizontal communication and its effectiveness

CULTURAL CHANGE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CHANGE EFFORTS OF DOUGLAS MACARTHUR AND CARLOS GHOSN IN JAPAN PDF: This is a comparative study on two companies of Japan in term of cultural change

Study on the impact of Information and Communications Technology(ICT) and New Media on_Language Learning: www.unaids.org. Guidelines and tools for developing communication strategies for joint UN team on AIDS: This a study of UN's communication strategies ,guidelines and tools which would be helpful in different development organisationsis a comparative study of opportunities, challenges, trends of ICT across European countries.

Article on Communication within Organisation by Michael Oldani:The article describes about the types of communication, its impact on organisation and scope for improvements.

K. Spaho: Organizational communication and conflict management; It is not possible to have good human relations without communication. An effective communication is required, not only for maintaining human relations, but also for achieving good business performance. In addition, practical experience shows that there is no communication without conflicts. Sometimes, conflicts can be useful, as they help to make correct decision, although they might represent a huge obstacle to an organization and its business. Firstly, some theoretical aspects of organizational communication will be presented, which is followed by discussion of selected theoretical aspects of conflicts and conflict management.

Kretschmer, T. (2012), "Information and Communication Technologies and productivity Growth: A Survey of the Literature", *OECD Digital Economy Papers*, No. 195,OECD Publishing.<http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/5k9bh3jllgs7-en>.This paper presents a review of existing studies on dynamic, macroeconomic effects of the ICT on productivity and growth.

Successful Communication:A tool kit for researchers: Developed under Research and Policy in development by ODI .ODI has developed a tool kit for success of communication in development organisations

Planning Tool:How to write communication strategies, developed and published by ODI:This article says about various communication tools used in development projects.

Research on Organisational communication, The case of Sweden by Catrin Johansson: In this article, a wide definition of organizational communication is employed, including research focusing on both internal and external communication. Research themes and methods are reviewed and discussed. The majority of the studies concern public information, including health communication and crisis communication.

www.orissawatershed.org. OWDM Publications and Working papers: The internal news letters and publications of Odisha Watershed Development Mission has been immensely helpful for getting past and present status of the organisation and its various communication processes.

www.worlp.com. :Working Paper-22 on Communication strategy for WORLP. Working Paper 66 on Knowledge Management & Communication Strategy for WORLP. Working Paper-60 on Institutional Arrangements for Capacity Building Delivery through WORLP. Working Paper-36 on Process

Documentation of WORLP is referred to have a clear picture of the organisation and its various activities related to communication.

Evolutionary Perspective of Watershed Projects: A watershed based development approach has been practiced in India for many decades by both government, non-government agencies, bilateral agencies, international aid and funding agencies. The primary aim of introducing this approach in the resource poor, rain-fed areas was to increase production. The evolution and emergence of watershed development in India can be attributed largely to the Green Revolution. Although the impact of large and medium irrigation projects resulted in large-scale agricultural production and promotion of allied activities, their effect could not be felt in rain-fed agricultural conditions in semi-arid tropical regions. It is estimated that nearly 65 % of the net sown area in the country is under rain-fed conditions [while the total geographical area of India is estimated to be 3290 lakh hectares, the total area under cultivation is 1730 lakh hectares]. Besides, the overall impact of irrigation-based projects has not always been encouraging though there have been a few exceptions. So, continuous attempts have been made to evolve an alternative mechanism to boost productivity in rain-fed conditions, especially because most of the rain-fed areas of the country are inhabited by the poorest and the most vulnerable population. A participatory watershed approach thus evolved, focusing on natural and livelihoods components such as water, land, agriculture, animal husbandry, forestry and other socio-economic factors, as part of overall development of a region. Accordingly, a new Department of Land Resources was created in April 1999, by the Ministry of Rural Development (MoRD) by merging different schemes.

Watershed projects are primarily implemented to improve the socio-economic condition of India's poorest farmers. Between 1975 and 1983, three pilot projects were launched with financing from the World Bank and its concessionary arm, the International Development Association [IDA], to improve agriculture in regions of India that lack irrigation. These were followed in 1984 by a pilot project for watershed development in rain-fed areas. Although the pilot programme generated significant advances, it could not be sustained over time. However, the lessons gained from this experience were incorporated right from the start, into the Integrated Watershed Development Projects. It initially provided for the development of about 2,50,000 hectares, covering eight watersheds with different soil types — two each in the states of Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, and Maharashtra. Although the project spurred experimentation and learning, it was uncertain whether the benefits could be sustained. The problems associated with such experimentation were mainly related to the lack of involvement of beneficiaries in project implementation, a lack of flexibility in project design and difficulties in replicating the model. Data on the costs and benefits of project interventions in individual watersheds were not maintained, thereby restricting the effectiveness of project monitoring and evaluation.

With increased learning from watershed experiences, a paradigm shift in the overall objective is marked in watershed implementation. Participatory means of watershed development has now become the focus, irrespective of differences in schemes. Now in all watersheds attempts are made to ensure people's participation from its inception to its end i.e. in planning, designing, implementation and also for follow-up of the programme at the end of the execution period. Along with the participatory approach, social and gender components were included into the execution framework.

Watersheds in Orissa: In Orissa, the concept of watershed was first introduced during the 2nd Five-Year Plan [1955-61] and refined during the 5th Plan through the Directorate of Soil Conservation. In the beginning of the 8th Plan, three major projects namely Integrated Watershed Development [plains] Project, National Watershed Development Project for Rainfed Areas [NWDPA] and Indo-Danish Comprehensive Watershed Development Project [IDCWDP] were launched in the State with the primary objectives to [1] Prevent land degradation, [2] Promote and balance the ecosystem, [3] Enhance capacity to retain moisture and [4] Increase the fertility and productivity of the soil.

Apart from this, watershed development projects were also implemented under other schemes including the Employment Assurance Scheme [EAS], Drought Prone Area Programmes [DPAP] and Integrated Wastelands Development Programme [IWDP] on a watershed basis. However, all these projects primarily

focused on water harvesting structures. Early indication of participatory watershed development projects in Orissa can be found in the IFAD supported OTDP Project and Indo-German Watershed Development (IGWD). Participatory watershed development programmes in Orissa evolved after the introduction of the revised watershed guidelines of 2001 developed by the Ministry of Rural Development, Government of India and JANASAHABHAGITA Guidelines of the Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India.

Novel and broader perspectives have started emerging with the experimentation of DFID aided Western Orissa Rural Livelihoods Project [WORLP]. Watersheds are now viewed as a suitable medium to improve the quality of life of poor people by means of creating sustainable opportunities for livelihood promotion in different avenues with the inclusion of a holistic and integrated approach, the expected beneficial results will be of a higher order, leading to improvement in the quality of life for poor people in the State.

The institutional structure of the OWDM is primarily framed at four different levels i.e. at state level, district level, block level and at the watershed level. The structure at state level is steering and advisory in nature that guides the overall programme execution and facilitating policy level implications. The 'Director' of the Watershed Development Mission is the executive head of the Mission at state level supported by Subject Matter Experts and Supervisory Experts. Consultants on requirement basis, support the Directorate on thematic areas. The District Collector is the Mission leader in the project execution districts and programme related decisions are taken in the watershed development committees formed at district level. There is also a provision for placing an exclusive person designated as 'Project Director, Watersheds in WORLP districts to carry forward the activities at district and watershed level. He/she is supported by the Assistant Project Directors (APDs) and Capacity Building Team (CBT).

The Project Implementing Agencies (PIAs) are significant in the whole structure as they are associated directly with the implementation of the programme at the block level. The Watershed Development Team, a technical arm of the PIA, is selected to facilitate the execution process of outlined watershed activities in an effective manner. For smooth operation of the programme in watershed areas and to ensure people's ownership and participation in a long term basis. Watershed Associations(WA) and Watershed Committees (WC) are formed with the support of the local community and PIAs.

In 2003, based on the proposition of Dr. B.N.Yugandhar, (ex-member, Planning Commission) the OWDM restructured itself and gradually evolved into an autonomous institution under the State Government. A post of 'Additional Director' was created to support the CEO (Director, Watershed Mission) in programme, administrative and financial matters. Independent responsibility of the Watershed Mission was given to the CEO without assigning any additional duties.

Based on the recommendations, the Watershed Mission also recruited technical managerial staff. These managers coordinate the Responsibility Centres (Technical, NRM, Training and Capacity Building, Livelihoods, Gender and Equity, Monitoring and Evaluation, GIS, MIS, etc)

Director-Additional Director-(Technology, NRM, M&E, Finance, P & A, Livelihoods, Gender Equity, Capacity Building, GIS, MIS are the responsibility centers of OWDM)

As WORLP is a government initiative, conscious attempts were made to facilitate the whole process keeping its distinct identity and ownership without compromising on design principles. In due course, the OWDM managed to retain its flexibility and innovative character. It has a combination of both lateral and vertical structures making it less hierarchal and more uniform for role convergence and functional clarity. Key among them have been the Capacity Building Team (CBT), the Livelihood Support Team (LST), the Watershed Development Team (WDT) and Community Link Workers (CLWs). The Project records multiple evolutions, where the principles of structural design are questioned very often and reworked from time to time to fulfill the set mandate. The PIAs work directly under the PD WS in the district. All remain under the control of Director, OWDM. The policies designed and the planned activities are directly communicated to the PD WS and subsequently communicated to the PIAs time to time.

Role of Communication in developmental organisations: Communication is an important medium in any development project which helps in information dissemination, awareness generation, circulating guidelines, recommendations, policy advocacy, promotion, education, conversation, roundtables, consultations, workshops, seminars, dialogue, counselling, entertainment, or increase knowledge on

various issues and finding solutions to them. Information is a tool that helps people help themselves, in a 'fishing-pole-rather-than-fish' sort of way. Instead of providing fish, we can teach them how to do fishing for their sustainable livelihoods. Information is the lever that people need to hold the organisation accountable and ensure transparency in participative and empowering processes. As one development communicator has put it 'they say sunlight is the best disinfectant, well let the sunlight in!' But in development projects, communication is often about more than providing information. It is about fostering social awareness, disseminating knowledge on project objectives as well as activities and facilitating public democratic dialogue. Communication is all about policy advocacy, documentation of best practices, and highlighting the success, failures, lessons learnt from the project. Effective Communication helps in wide outreach and building a shared understanding which can lead to social change. It is about creating space for the voices of the poor to be heard. However, these positive effects of communication do not come automatically. More communication does not mean more development. In fact, in certain situations, obscure and inaccurate information can *obstruct the* development process in a community. Thus success of any project depends on proper documentation and communication activities. In this context, Odisha Watershed Development Mission is taken for a comparative analysis of communication in the past with the present. In Odisha Watershed Development Mission under the aegis of Western Orissa Rural Livelihood Project various communication strategies were adopted for better delivery and outreach of project activities. Poor communication outreach led to failure of development projects. So in order to avoid this utmost importance was given for developing a proper communication strategy in Western Orissa Rural Livelihood Project (WORLP).

Problem Statement:

Initially Orissa Watershed Development Mission did not have proper working modalities and operational Guidelines on management of watershed projects. The staffs did not have adequate knowledge and expertise on management of different projects resulting in poor work quality and Planning. Poor organisational structure and lack of team work led to poor progress. Communication was limited within few departmental staffs of the organisation. The organisation did not show any interest for building capacity of Managers, Assistant Managers, supervisors and the district level staffs. Less transparency and poor accountability were there. There was not adequate resource for printing and publication purpose. Performing Arts in the form of Street Plays and local folk art was not getting enough attention. However the various organisational problems related to communication are written below.

- Poor Work Quality and Planning
- Lack of Team Work
- Insufficient Resources within
- Lack of Support from the Government
- Lack of knowledge and awareness on Project Guidelines
- Exchange of Information was very low and time consuming
- Inadequate Capacity Building events for the project staff as well as community
- Limited Outreach of communication materials in remote rural pockets (Information did not flow down)
- Performing Arts not getting enough attention.

Objective of the Study:

- To compare the communication process adopted in OWDM in the past with the present
- To know about various communication strategy adopted during the implementation of WORLP.

Assumptions /Hypothesis

- Communication is central to the existence of the organisation.
- Proper communication strategy helps in increasing organisational effectiveness.

Research Methodology:

Personal Discussions, interviews, small interactions with the employees of Odisha Watershed Development Mission and the project staffs. The research is more of qualitative in nature by going through the past history of the organisation with the present situation with some of its future implication.

IDENTIFICATION OF COMMUNICATION NEEDS

Keeping view of the above problems in the organisation the project showed its keenness for a concerted and coordinated effort to develop an effective communication strategy for the community as well as the project staffs. As a result of which a consultation meeting with all the stakeholders was organised to identify and assess the communication needs. During the consultation, various issues were come out related to communication and which need to be addressed immediately.

Messages are currently being given orally in the community. They need to be backed up by a variety of communication tools. Messages are conveyed primarily by the PIAs and the WDTs to all the villages in each watershed. Messages given with a touch of humour are appreciated. Cartoons are more appealing to the community than realistic images.

Issues which need to be communicated to the community:

- What is a watershed?
- What are the components of the watershed?
- What are the objectives, goals and activities of WORLP?
- What is the Project's exit strategy? How will the Project interventions be sustained by the community after the Project withdraws?
- What are the schemes of various line departments which the community can continue to access even when the Project withdraws?
- How can the community be made to understand land-based activities for soil and water conservation?
- What are the success stories? What are the failures, problems and shortcomings? Have they been addressed? Lessons learnt and documentation of best practices and whether these have been properly disseminated?
- How is WORLP addressing gender? Are women feeling more empowered through the formation of groups? What are the changes needed in the areas of health, literacy, empowerment, gender and equity?

Like the community, staffs at the State, District and Block levels need a clearer understanding of the Project. Information should be available in both English and Oriya. They should be made aware on

- What is the difference between WORLP and other watershed projects? What does 'watershed plus' mean?
- What are the salient points of the Project Memorandum? What are the contents of the current revised log-frame?
- What are the guidelines of GoI, GoO and the Project?
- Project staff must understand that there are certain Do's and Don'ts in the Project e.g. SHGs should not be just for women; Watershed Committees should be formed only after SHGs have been established; a livelihood option should build on the strength of the community member; gender, environment and equity must cut across every initiative.
- What is the Watershed Development Fund rules/percentage of contribution? What are the fund-flow mechanisms?
- How will the government, NGOs and the community manage after the donor funded project withdraws? What are the indicators of sustainability?
- What are the guidelines for preparing a micro-plan?
- What are the specific roles and responsibilities of each staff member?
- What are the agreed lines of communication between the different levels of the Project?

However Some of the more general issues are:

- Project staff should share experiences, limitations, challenges, conflict resolution, best practices, new initiatives and lessons.

- Changes in guidelines and circulars issued by GoI, GoO, and OWDM must reach the district and block levels without delay, in Oriya as well as English.
- Project staff, NGOs and government line departments should communicate so that there is convergence between the different stakeholders.
- Community participation plays a vital role in the success of the Project. This message should be sent to all levels.
- Currently all reporting from the field to the state level of the Project is format based. There is no space for qualitative or subjective reporting.
- Project staff need to strengthen their communication skills – verbal, presentation and written. Regular updation of website and use of E-mails for easy outreach.

COMMUNICATIONS STRATEGY:

To address various needs of the organisation as well as its stakeholders a number of communication strategies were taken up for effective communication and wide outreach. However the communication channels identified are:

- Printed material;
- Audio-visual material;
- Electronic media;
- Workshops and conferences;
- Performing arts.

PRINTED MATERIAL

An Introduction to WORLP provides a broad brush view of WORLP to those who need an introduction to the Project. This would include staff in the Project, from the block level, to the state level; visitors, consultants to the Project; GoO officials from other departments; GoI officials; people from other projects, institutions and organisations from within and outside the country.

What is WORLP enables project staff from the block level downwards, and the community, to understand the philosophy behind the Project and what it means to them in real terms.

Internal Newsletters are primarily a tool for exchange of information within the Project. It will allow staff of the Project to communicate with each other and disseminate information which could be of use to other people within the Project. This is specially useful where there is no one-on-one channel of communication available to all the staff in the Project. Connected government departments, DFID and other organisations could also be kept in the loop.

Community Newsletter: Since communication is a two-way process, newsletters are the medium in which voice of the community is heard. It allows the project staff to reach out to the community. This newsletter would apprise the external stakeholders of what is happening at the grass roots level in the Project.

Technical bulletins/Training Materials will help to throw light on various themes such as Natural Resource Management, Livelihoods, Socio-Capital restoration etc. Details of topic is to be work out. Training Materials would also help in enlightening the knowledge and awareness level of various stake holders in the project.

Audio Visual Materials in the form of short films, posters, flip charts could be used as a tool for building awareness and capacity. In development projects while working with the community, audio-visual material is more effective than the printed materials. Showcasing innovations and films lasting from two minutes to half an hour should be specially made to sensitize the community on new ideas and technology. Themes could be on Participatory planning, Soil and water conservation, NTFP processing and marketing, Institution Building, New methodologies in agriculture and aquaculture, Health and sanitation etc. There should be a consultation between staff at state, district and block levels to decide where these films could be shown to the community. Films must be dubbed in the local dialect.

AV materials also help in showcasing WORLP's work to the outside world. Once the Project starts achieving its objectives, this medium should be used to capture good stories. These would be broadcast in the media, during conferences and workshops and any forum where policy-makers gather, in order to project WORLP's image and to influence policy. The consultant should work with the Project staff and the film maker to ensure accuracy and quality.

Flip charts are relatively low cost aids for use, especially in community mobilisation. Once again Project staff should be consulted on how and when they could use these tools. They will have to work out the various themes in detail so that these could be converted into pictorial stories. Project staffs have to be trained to use them effectively.

Posters: Films and flip charts are presented for a short time to the community, but to strengthen the message a series of posters which tell the same story should be left behind on the walls of the community meeting halls. Posters for the community should be brightly coloured, attractive and pictorial with a minimum amount of text. Children can be the agents of change. Posters which teach a variety of lessons could be created especially for children and put up in the schools in the watershed areas.

Electronic Media in the form of website and E-mails can be used for outreach of communication activities. WORLP website needs to be strengthened in terms of design and content. It should be updated regularly so that material such as newsletters and reports are put on the site as soon as they have been produced. A specialist – a consultant or an organisation – should be entrusted with this work. E-mails should also be used to exchange information, specially internal reports, memo and bulletins, within the Project. However, it is to be noted that the electronic media has a limited reach and should not be used for any communication aimed at the grass-roots level.

Workshops and Group meetings should be used for exchange of information and communication between the stakeholders within the Project. They could be subject related and tagged on to the visit of a consultant; they could be regular time-bound meetings to facilitate exchange of knowledge between staff. Bearing in mind the heavy work-loads of staff these workshops should not become an end in themselves, but only a means to an end, preferably demand-led by staff. Workshops for external invitees should be aimed not only at an exchange of information, but as an opportunity to present WORLP and its achievements to the outside world.

Performing Arts is one of the best medium for community mobilisation and awareness building in rural area. A street play is a very powerful tool, especially where lifestyle and attitudes need to be addressed. A street play covers themes such as gender sensitivity, unity, social evils such as drinking and dowry, the advantages of saving, literacy etc. Troupes in Orissa should be identified. They should be able to adapt their scripts to the local dialect. Similarly the project could organise celebrity shows (film star, singer, and dancer) in which the celebrity tries to communicate project messages. This is mainly to draw the community towards the projects goal and objectives in the form of games, quizzes, songs, dance shows where the community participates fully. This will need meticulous planning but is invaluable in terms of rural communication.

Sample Study & the process of Data Collection:

The researcher has tried to analyse and compare a project called Western Orissa Rural Livelihoods Project of Odisha Watershed Development Mission, the structure and flow of communication in the past with the present. Literature survey was made to gather information and relevant data and also to have adequate knowledge on the subject Organisational Communication.

Activities undertaken to improve workplace communication

Earlier much capacity building trainings were not organised for the project staffs and community. So the staffs and community members were not aware about the project, its aim, objectives and other aspects. Communication in the form of books, newsletters, websites was not there. Communication was limited

within few project staffs. Cross functional meetings, group discussions and cross functional meetings were not organised. No effort was taken to improve the organisational communication. When WORLP came a series of interventions were made to improve the workplace communication in the following areas,

- Training to the senior level management/employees/Specialists of all thematic areas
- Training for mid-level managers/Asst Managers/Supervisors/Team leaders
- Cross functional meetings, discussions, brainstorming on various project related issues
- Workshops, seminars, national and state level consultations to share the project output
- Publications (books, newsletters, Working papers, printing and Audiovisual aids)

Present Organisational Set Up

Odisha Watershed Development Mission has been notified as the State Level Nodal Agency (SLNA) and the Director, Watershed Mission has been designated as the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) of SLNA for implementation of IWMP watershed projects in the state. Managers and Assistant Managers of OWDM provide managerial and administrative support to watershed mission. Contractual professionals i.e. Technical Experts (Subject Matter Specialists) have been positioned at the OWDM for SLNA to provide necessary technical support.

To strengthen the delivery mechanism at the district level, Project Director (watersheds) offices have been created in twenty-six districts where Integrated Watershed Management Programme (IWMP) and Jeebika programme are under implementation. Project Director (Watersheds) in the rank of Deputy Director, Soil Conservation (Class-I, Sr. Branch) is being assisted by a team of Assistant Project Directors i.e. APDs (government officers in the rank of Class-II) along with contractual professionals such as Technical Experts (TEs) /Subject Matter Specialist (SMS). In case of implementation of state funded Jeebika Programmes, Capacity Building Teams (CBTs) are in position. The APDs provide administrative and managerial support where as SMSs/TEs provide necessary technical support to the Project Implementing Agencies (PIAs) and to the technical team at the cluster level for watershed implementation in the field of Livelihoods, Natural Resources Management (NRM), Monitoring & Evaluation (M&E) and Finance.

At the Cluster level, Project Implementing Agencies (PIAs) have been engaged exclusively to facilitate implementation of watershed projects. Each PIA is assigned with one cluster having 10-12 watersheds covering an area of 5000-6000 ha which is a well manageable unit for effective implementation of the programme. Each PIA is supported with a team of Watershed Management Team (WMT) and a team of Livelihoods Support Team (LSTs) in case of state funded Jeebika projects. The PIAs, WMTs and LSTs are engaged in full time basis to provide technical and hand holding support to the Watershed Committee (WCs) at the watershed level for smooth implementation of the programme.

Impact

After this set up flow of Communication from top to bottom was transparent and each of the staffs was given individual role and responsibility to perform. The Project Support Unit (PSU) was established to provide strategic support to Director, Watershed Mission in each thematic areas like Livelihoods, Natural Resource Management, Information Technology, Capacity Building, Communication, Social Development & Gender. For better implementation, Director Watershed Mission reviews the performance of PD Watersheds and the PIAs through Video Conferencing in collaboration with ORSAC. Monthly and Quarterly meetings are organised to monitor the project activities. During the meeting the PIAs and PDs also give feedback to Director about the new ideas, difficulties and effectiveness of the project. For better Communication and transparency and accountability between the state, district, and block level officials, Capacity Building Team members (CBT) in various disciplines were appointed at the district level to avoid any communication gap among the stake holders of watershed project. Watershed Development Team (WDT) members were appointed to work under Project Implementing Agencies in different thematic areas. WDTs supervised the work of the community link workers (CLW) who worked in close contact of community and with different community level institutions like Watershed Association (WA), Watershed Committee (WC), Self Help Groups (SHG), User Groups (UG), Common Interest Groups (CIG) etc. Hence organisation structure with a proper communication strategy is very important for smooth delivery of

work. These WDTs played a catalytic role in project implementation, sharing information and communicating ideas within the community.

A number of capacity Building events on each thematic areas, seminars, workshops, state and district level consultations were organised to spread the message (both success and failures of the project) to the stakeholders outside of the project including Government Organisations, Non-Government Organisations, and Civil Society Organisations. During these events sharing of ideas, exchange of information took place and everyone got to know about the project and its various objectives. With increased knowledge and awareness and proper information dissemination, the performance of the project staffs also geared up. Communication activities were strengthened which helped in creating a visual image of WORLP in the whole world .The success of DFID's WORLP in Orissa brought high recognition among other development projects and recently it has been rated as Green by the Independent Commission for Aid Impact(ICAI) community.(The fund reached and directly benefited 62% out of the total 32.75 million dollar project fund for poor rural community in terms of loans and grants).

Output

As a result of communication strategy Workshops & Conferences were organized for sharing of experiences and learning . Livelihood Resource Center Network (LRCN) was established in the district for proper flow of information at the community level through series of trainings and awareness programmes . The communication materials published in the form of Printed Materials & Audio-Visual Materials. Official websites are properly managed and regularly updated by the organization. Use of electronic media is more now a days in comparison to earlier years.

Replication & Future Implications

The success of this project with the structure is now replicated in other Government Departments. Many development projects are taking inspiration from WORLP, and its communication materials are used in all the Government Departments of Odisha. All the departments are setting up Project Support Unit and Project Management Unit in line with OWDM's WORLP. People are going for exposures to WORLP districts to see the successes so that it can be replicated in their areas.

Recommendations

- Inclusive ,holistic and integrated approach with a proper communication strategy will lead to success of any development organisation/project
- WORLP model is to be replicated in all other projects of Watershed Mission
- More and more communication outputs will help in wide outreach, increase knowledge and awareness of stake holders in development projects.
- Transparency and accountability is to be ensured in all the levels of organisational structure.
- Organisation ownership/community ownership need to be given utmost importance.

Conclusion

To summarize and conclude the researcher has given apt justification to the hypothesis formulated in the beginning of the comparative study of communication in any organisation. The project developed a justifiable solution to understand the complex communication process within an organisation which is being influenced by a diversity of factors. Proper communication is highly required for effective functioning of any organisation. The study gives scope for other researchers who are interested to do research in communication in development organisations.

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List of Abbreviations

OWDM	Orissa Watershed Development Mission
IDA	International Development Association
DFID	Department Fund For International Development
NWDPRA	National Watershed Development Project for Rainfed Areas
IDCWDP	Indo-Danish Comprehensive Watershed Development Project
EAS	Employment Assurance Scheme
DPAP	Drought Prone Area Programmes
IWDP	Integrated Wastelands Development Programme
IGWD	Indo-German Watershed Development
OTDP	Orissa Tribal Development Project
WORLP	Western Orissa Rural Livelihoods Project
APD	Assistant Project Directors
CBT	Capacity Building Team
PIA	Project Implementing Agency
WDT	Watershed Development Team
WMT	Watershed Management Team
WA	Watershed Association
WC	Watershed Committee
SHG	Self Help Group
UG	User Group
CLW	Community Link Worker
LST	Livelihoods Support Team Member
PSU	Project Support Unit
LRCN	Livelihood Resource Center Network
ICAI	Independent Commission for Aid Impact
GIS	Geographic Information System
MIS	Management Information System
GoO	Government of Orissa
GOI	Government of India
IFAD	International Fund For Agricultural Development
ORSAC	Orissa Remote Sensing Application Center
IWMP	Integrated Watershed Management Programme
MoRD	Ministry of Rural Development
NRM	Natural Resource Management
PD WS	Project Director,Watersheds
WDC	Watershed Development Committee
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
SMS	Subject Matter Specialist